

SYNTHESIS OF SOME CHALKONE-2: 4-DINITROPHENYLHYDRAZONES

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The usual derivatives used for the characterisation of carbonyl compounds are oxime, semicarbazone and 2: 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. The last derivative appears to be of special significance for the characterisation of chalcones on account of the relative ease of its formation. With that end in view the 2: 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones of several chalcones were prepared. The results are reported in this communication (Table I).

TABLE I

2: 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazone.	Colour & cryst. shape	Crystallised from.	M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
2-Hydroxychalkone-	Brick-red, micro-needles	EtAc	228	$C_{21}H_{18}O_5N_4$	14.0	13.86
3-Hydroxychalkone-	Bright red, micro-needles	„	233	$C_{21}H_{18}O_5N_4$	13.98	13.86
4-Hydroxychalkone-	Bright-red, ** rectangular and hexagonal prisms	„	231-32.5	$C_{21}H_{18}O_5N_4$	13.64	13.86
2'-Hydroxychalkone-	Orange, micro-needles	„	236-37°	$C_{21}H_{18}O_5N_4$	14.0	13.86
2'-Hydroxy-2-methoxychalkone-	Orange-red, rod type crystals	„	225-26°	$C_{22}H_{18}O_6N_4$	13.0	12.90
2'-Hydroxy-3-methoxychalkone-	Orange-red, stellate aggregate of micro-needles	Xylene	209	$C_{22}H_{18}O_6N_4$	12.95	12.90
2'-Hydroxy-3: 4-dimethoxychalkone-	Brick-red, microcrystalline mass	Ethanol	215-17	$C_{23}H_{20}O_7N_4$	12.24	12.06
2-Methoxychalkone-	Vermilion, hexagonal plates	EtAc	218-19°	$C_{23}H_{18}O_6N_4$	13.20	13.39
3-Methoxychalkone-	Deep red, microcrystalline powder	EtOH-acetone	214-15	$C_{22}H_{18}O_5N_4$	13.41	13.39
4-Methoxychalkone-	Orange, slender, micro-needles	EtAc	245-46	$C_{22}H_{18}O_5N_4$	13.49	13.39
3':4-Dimethoxychalkone-	Red, micro-needles	„	249-50°	$C_{23}H_{20}O_7N_4$	12.65	12.50

** Pyrochromatic, dark red-hot.

The chalcones required in this investigation were synthesised according to the procedure of Schraufstätter and Deutsch (*Chem. Ber.*, 1948, **81**, 489). The 2: 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones were prepared by the general method, (Wild, "Characterisation of Organic Compounds", Cambridge University Press, 1947, p. 112) using a solution of the reagent in sulphuric acid and employing a slight excess of the carbonyl compound.

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